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Genetic Brand Strategies and Consumer Satisfaction of Therapeutic Industry in Rivers State

Prof. Sunny R, Igwe¹, Prince Obina Ikechi Ph.D², Chinwe D.E, Amadi³, Edwin O Asikihia⁴ & Adama Idakwo Sanusi⁵

Department of Marketing, Faculty of Management Sciences
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education,
Rumuolumeni, Port-Harcourt, Nigeria.

Email: chinweamadi556@gmail.com, Aisanusi11@gmail.com, & asizebu@yahoo.com

Phone; 07060941978

ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between genetic brand strategies and customer satisfaction of the pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State. The study adopted the correlation design. The study adopted the census approach as well undertook a study of the (21) among the registered pharmaceutical companies marketing managers in Rivers state. Sixty three (63) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the twenty one pharmaceutical companies. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used. From the bivariate analysis carried, it was noted that genetic brand strategies showed a positive and significant relationship with customer satisfaction of pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State. It was revealed that genetic brand strategies showed a very strong significant relationship with customer satisfaction. The life style/aspiration showed a moderate significant relationship with customer satisfaction. The study concludes that genetic brand strategies have a very strong relationship with brand heritage /tradition also the personalization and customization are significant predictor of customer satisfaction in pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State. The study recommends that. Pharmaceutical therapeutic industry should engage in genetic brand strategies as another, to enable them profitably gain good portraying in their industrial decision making in the pharmaceutical therapeutic services.

Keywords: Genetic, Brand Strategies, Customer Satisfaction, Pharmaceutical, Therapeutic, Industry

INTRODUCTION

Genetic brand strategies which involves using genetic information for marketing purpose, is relatively a new and rapid evolving area of knowledge cut off in September 2017 there is not a specific individual or company that can be definitively identified as first to work on genetic marketing research in previous years.

This therapeutic industry is operating under the structure of the oligopoly market. It is made up of a group of strong vital medical companies. Where the smaller companies are under the covering as routinely acquired by registered member. Meaning that it is a market structure where a small number of producers work to restrict output or fix prices to enable them achieve efficiently and above others the in same industry.

Brand is a brain power of every product or service. The brain to the unique power of identity CVS HEALTH. (2019) considered the need for customer satisfaction, swiftly rebranded service image by converting the known pharmaceutical therapeutic industry to CVS Healthcare (2019). This to a quick brain power of how brand can change content using the genetic concept to satisfy the present and future need of human. Such swift became sustainable during the pandemic of (COVID19), the company was not only providing drugs but went into other genetic segment of the therapeutic services the genetic brand strategies refers to brand building approaches that are genetically inbuilt in the DNA of every brand as an essential factor. The aims of the genetic brand strategies are to leverage the unique characteristics, values and heritage of any brand, this is creating a substantial or a distinct

and authentic identify vibrate with the uniqueness of brand. The genetic brand strategies involves1) heritage and tradition.

Authenticity and Transparency innovation and cutting edge, life style and aspiration personalization and customization. It shows the worth of genetic brand strategies to the effectiveness of brand management. CIM (2007) BRAND is more than logos or names. They are the culmination of a user's total experience with the product, it is simply the experience the product performs.

Davison and Chinwe (2021) genetically genetic brand is the first basis for the thought of brand. The real facts of the rooted cause in branding. To unearth a brand. Meaning that every physical differentiation to it phenotype. The trait of products are the bases interpretation to what genetic brand is. We can say brand can be measured with feeling, motivation and satisfaction. Genetic brand has no exclusive definition; it could be defined as it is relating department of marketing in Nigerian universities, not concluding, this is the first article in genetic brand strategies in my university at the present.

Concept of genetic brand strategies involves empirical service records, geographical market and demographical resource, in other to determine the segmentation of the market health, beauty, nutrition, products and services. Geographical concepts is the strength base on environmental analysis market and product thought test. The geographical context and healthy content dictate's the continuous process in the geographical market which will require the longevity proceeds that announce the healthy procession in the marketing services. Demographical resource is typically the market audience. The people in general content. The consumer's acceptability, classes of demographic-mix, and brand usefulness, which indicates the contextual usage.

In the terms of request bases on choice which involve, types, size, age, potent as regards to genetic market testing of the pharmaceuticals brand and products. Andrew (2021) admits that the origin of branding in business terms lies with the need for groups and individuals to have identity that was easily recognisable by others. This started as a military application but soon spread to guide and master craft men who made special good products. This continued with manufacturers who could provide consistent quality goods who noticed that making them easier to recognise. With the expansion of the trade, brands became necessary as a mark of quality assurance. Is also agreed or may be argued that brand can be identified as quality of a status experience with a product.

Brand calls for branding concept or activities. The process that brand undergo, for awareness by creating experience to the consumers is called branding. Daviet, Caro and Chinwe (2019) note that the use of third party interpretation services, which is the act of gaining a potent provision with more information based on consumer products protection and disease risk, trait and brand ancestry. The possible need for genetic brand strategies and consumer satisfaction, brand information is to promote Brand, productions and customer satisfaction services as infinite to genetic brand strategic variation among consumers.

In view of the above shared knowledge. Genetic brand is as old as age. As every brand produce was first groomed from the creation of every living organism where brands shade It is first evidence in the features as physical presentation. That brought about difference in all physical presentation and in their ability and functions to indicate their nature and strength potentials, in brand colour and shape, in plants, animals and human. Also related to the heritage/tradition of our genetic environment, it became the bases for application of difference. In the geographical areas, the heritage/tradition genetic data also became a brand life style that aspires the personalization/customization for consumer satisfaction.

Whaley (2020) observed that the strength of customer relationship that bounds satisfaction with a brand is central to the brand's growth. The Brand activities which establishes a relationship has prompted companies to develop a two-way flow of various relationship building communication with their customers and encourage to integrate brands into their life. Brand is a base name of any product that has it root on its kind of brand and purpose, that the consumers experience. Brand satisfaction sounds generic, but satisfaction could mean differently to consumers. In that, genetic brand strategies and consumer satisfaction is a genetic potent value of what the Brand does for consumers.

Customer satisfaction is basically in all the need and choice of any user. While the therapeutic industrial brand means the producers of the pharmaceutical (medical) equipment or drugs for healing or controlling health condition that meet with brand need and satisfaction. Every brand serves as a genetic foundation of purpose for satisfaction. It could be a long term satisfaction or a short time satisfaction. But there must a level of satisfaction for every brand. That is the clear reason all brand have its purpose to close a gap. Looking into the world of creation God created them male and female and blessed them with a mandate for multiplication, before then God has already made a programmed system and conditions for satisfaction of his purpose of making them male and female. This model of creation with the terms and conditions applied are known as strategies to consumer satisfaction (Igwe, 2016) While the genetic brand concept is the phenotype of brand which is male brand and the female brand. Genetically there are baselines for genetic brand and consumer satisfaction of therapeutic industry.

(SAO PAULO (2018) New York Brand Are Genetically Growth Seekers, in (1996) all marketing was Darwinian industry using the genetic brand strategies, of evolutionary genetic approach for innovation, using the concept to understand the DNA of what makes consumers unique remains at the heart of human first insight and innovation at work. At brand genetics it is believed that the future is human the use of a human –first approach to insight and innovation as the way to help producers understand what consumers will want next and then champion positive innovation as the way forward, innovating for consumer happiness and wellbeing. Following these four core predict of genetic brand strategies. The genetic brand strategies basically involves the quantitative approaches, this approach is the energy behind the thought and origins for realistic innovation and brand heritage/tradition on genetic brand concept.

The four Distinct or Brand Exploration

- i. Heritage and Tradition of Brand
- ii. Life Style and Tradition for Brand
- iii. Authenticity and Aspiration of Brand
- iv. Personalization and Customization to Brand

To understand the direction of change, in the genetic brand strategic concept to gain customer satisfaction most relate to the five genetic brand principles as a strategic tool to customer satisfaction. The modern concepts of branding developed, alongside marketing as a managerial process, off which some of the known brands initially existed as companies before the branding concept. Evidently, brand has raised a wealth of quality value and as well becomes the performance cues and portray a dynamic and unique experience as a part of a consumers life style. Like Apple will say their product identifies as a life style not just a phone, the genetic brand strategies are the possible means to ripple customer satisfaction. Strategies to focus on this study using the psychological human motivation to genetic brand, focusing on brand heritage /tradition, life style/aspiration and personalization/customization, of the therapeutic industry not finding the consumers brand loyalty to experience customer satisfaction, as a result to the fear of the future effect of therapeutic medications or kits, the human psychological motivation has reduced or deplete due to human low empathy to the potent measures of therapeutic product. Which has actually trigger the retrogress of consumer satisfaction.

Statement of the Problem

Genetic Brand Strategies become the link to create customer satisfaction in the therapeutic industry in Rivers State. The therapeutic industry are not sensitive to consumer's brand heritage/tradition to experience customer satisfaction, as a result due to lack of brand heritage and tradition knowledge the, personalization/ customization to improve life style and aspiration of customer satisfaction effectiveness of pharmaceutical therapeutic medications or kits, the human psychological motivation has reduced or deplete due to human low merge with brand heritage and tradition. The potent measures of therapeutic product, which has actually trigger the retrogress of consumer satisfaction. An investigation carried out by NDLEA on the 6th of October (2023.) The statement also revealed that another drug trafficker, named Nwafor Charles, was arrested in Abuja airport and being places for observation, did excreted 75 pellets of cocaine, weighing 1.653kgs. Source punch newspaper 15th October (2023). More investigation on some pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State, revealed that the fear of the future affects

pharmaceutical therapeutic brand in Rivers State, has made their customers motivationally empathetic and the human future in debris, heritage and tradition is reflecting approach and avoidance to motives, that states either encourage consumers to engage with the brand or to avoid the brand experience. The therapeutic industry, not finding the consumers brand loyalty to experience customer satisfaction, as a result to the life style and aspiration effect, of therapeutic medications or kits, the human psychological motivation has reduced or deplete due to human low empathy to the potent measures of therapeutic product. Actually looking forward to personalization and customization of consumers satisfaction of pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State, which has led to the useful research, poling the genetic brand strategies as a key driving for consumer satisfaction in the pharmaceutical therapeutic industry.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The study aim was to investigate the relationship between customer satisfaction and genetic brand strategies of pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

- 1) Investigate the extent of relationship between genetic brand strategies and brand heritage/tradition to brand of pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State.
- 2) Determine the relationship between consumers satisfaction and life brand heritage and tradition.

Research questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the study

- 1) What is the extent of the relationship between genetic brand strategies and brand heritage/tradition to brand of pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State?
- 2) What is the extent of the relationship between consumers’ satisfaction and life brand heritage and tradition?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated to be tasted.

- 1) Ho1: There are no significant relationship between brand heritage / tradition and personalization Customization
- 2) Ho2: There are no significant relationship between life style/ aspiration and consumer satisfaction personalization Customization

Conceptual Framework

The Alliance Brand Genetic Concept: Brand Genetic; known as brand innovative company is a member of the independent agencies. It is a vibrant community for those marketing agencies that are independent in culture and entrepreneurial in spirit resulting in creation of some of the most transformative, innovative and inspirational communication campaigns for the world’s biggest brands

Fig.1.1 Conceptual framework of Genetic Brand Strategies and customer satisfaction.

Source: (23& me, (2020); CVS Healthcare 2022).

Review of Related Literature

Genetic brand strategies driving for customer satisfaction are the bases of this work to peruse the focus and intense need for genetic brand strategies towards marketing education, theories and customer satisfaction concept. Hassan (2018) Mexico's national air carrier Aero Mexico, launched a DNA brand discount, campaign offering to some customers that matched the travellers Mexico DNA percentage, determined by a genetic test. (Vera 2019) these action marked dawn of a new age when consumers and firms alike access information on genetic brand information, was rarely accessible by the measured of human genome in brand satisfaction with the aid of genetic brand strategy made it useful to allocate and group consumers accordable, which made the genome market segmentation to brand heritage/tradition to achieve consumer satisfaction. Such data are now viable through the direct to consumer genetic testing (Direct to Consumers and Genetic Testing (DTC-GT) market, that increased consumer satisfaction in (2019) most patronage came from the therapeutic brand kits such as DNA test kits. Plastic tubes, smart kits for blood pressure and TP test kits consumers spite into it and then ship off for genomic analysis to uncover forgotten family history to accessing genetic predispositions for diseases. As of (2020) more than thirty million people have already taken the personalised DNA Test (Regalado 2019). A by-product of growing direct to consumer Genetic test (DTC-GT) Market is on the high increase of massive genetic data set brands. The 23 and me therapeutic industry encouraged consumers to participate in the search by answering the survey about a brand dietary habits and personality. (Farr 2020) the DCT-GT companies are aiming to monetized their data to maintain growth and customer satisfaction (Bowden 2018) 23 and me has already accredited access to its data to the pharmaceuticals company GlaxoSmith line currently it is believing that the genetic brand strategies are of prevailing factor to consumer satisfaction. Guinn (2021) first coined the term brand community and they defined it as; a specialised brand, Brand community, based on a structure set of social relations among the Brand Heritage/ Tradition motivational team segment of pharmaceutical.

Industry in Rivers State are slacking in motivational empathy to brand heritage/tradition, if they apply the heritage and personalization, life style and aspiration ploy to their therapeutic brand, it will encourage customer satisfaction. Kotler and Zelman have commented that even products with obvious value to a society, such as free medical care, pollution control or public transportation, must be presented with understanding of consumer behaviour and sophistication in the marketing programmes, if the products are to be accepted by the societies life style /aspiration are basically justified in the geographical perception, human culture and human believe, are the bases, so that to be considered when a brand is about to serve a particular geographical zone. Personalisation/customization are those characteristics that human display towards brand. Ezirim (2015) and Kotler (2014) have revealed the need for public policy on consumer awareness and need to create the need for choice and choice cannot be overemphasis inhuman behaviour. Choice of brand is a genetic attribute to human behaviour, where brand is genetically desired or fits to gain customer satisfaction, the human behaviour grave for brand loyalty, for a period. The pharmaceutical industry has a great opportunity if utilised by adopting the genetic brand strategies for customer satisfaction.

The Significant of the Study

This study will be relevant to various categories of person or group of firms and organisation mostly in the instant and further studies, it will be useful in decision making of pharmaceutical therapeutic brand procurement, due to the effective quantitative information and survey experience as it will guide to address some level of uncertainties, such as geographical and demographical factors related to customer satisfaction.

On how to satisfy the consumer through the reveal of personalization/ Customization and consumer satisfaction that will enhance the pharmaceutical therapeutic industry practitioner to understand brand heritage/ tradition for the present and future brand knowledge and increase life style and audience. Also the study will be relevant to the researchers that have interest in genetic marketing research and brand management, entrepreneurial practice as well in the faculty of management sciences.

Scope of the study

The scope of this study are categorized in to three parts: The unit of the study analysis is the pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State. The content scope of the study was on the relationship between genetic brand strategies and customer satisfaction. The geographical scope of the study was limited to marketing managers of pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Genetic brand strategies

Chinwe (2020) observed that Genetic Brand Strategies are used to identify brand heritage/tradition personalization/customization, to dictate lifestyle and aspiration of brand and consumers that shows the authentication/transparency, innovation /cutting edge. Genetic brand strategies are found obtainable in positioning brand decision making for customer satisfaction, which is not limited to the pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State. Literatures related to the independent variable as genetic brand strategies the dependent variable, customer satisfaction and its measures are viewed also life style/aspiration the moderating variable and Heritage/Tradition to brand.

Dimensions of Genetic Brand Strategies

Genetic Branding Strategies: Dimensions of Genetic Brand Strategies used in this study are brand heritage/tradition, life style/aspiration, personalization / customization though the strategies of genetic brand strategies are of five dimensions including innovation /cutting- edge and authenticity/transparency. Which will be added to this work in anticipation. *Source; genetic trend human first- (2022) Genetic Brand Marketing*

Brands heritage /tradition: The brand heritage is the positioning of brand long history that emphasized their legacy as core part of their genetic brand value. It high light the tradition, time, taste quality and credibility which evoked consumer royalty. It emphasised on legacy as a core part of their genetic brand strategy (Chinwe 2018).

Personalization/customization;

Whaley (2020) Most brands differentiate themselves by offering highly personalized and customized experiences, they focus on understanding their customer's individual needs and references allowing them to tailor their products or services to provide a unique and personalized experience. The genetic brand strategy with the tool personalization/customization aims to create a strong bound between the brand and the consumers, to gain customer satisfaction; this is an act of going outside the box to make the consumers kind of brand that attest to the adornment of the customer in other to win satisfaction of the customer while the brand attracts the loyalty of the customer. Via customization to achieve the desired personalization as could gain of the brand genetic impression.

Customer/Satisfaction: Igwe (2019) the consumer satisfaction is shaped by social and cultural forces that merges with wealth of health heritage and tradition to aid a personalization lifestyle. eg. The Aqua-Ibom's are known to be strong and healthy personality due to their tradition and heritage of herbs and vegetables personalization life style. Which was gain during the Europeans era in Calabar as said by elder James Akpan (2005) of pharmaceutical business with a more specific aspirational values will be associated with need for satisfaction. CVS (2020) modifies the customers monopoly need to various models of CVS Health care giver. Their service employed a culture that service in five different health areas, genetically it provided all the genetic data of a client in one file multiple in the health care service with different departments but same genetic environment of CVS Health Care Brands. Customer satisfaction are measured with following concept of service

1. Attractiveness
2. Job flexibility and potent
3. Affordable
4. Also sufficiently available

Life style and aspiration

These brands align themselves with specific values or aspiration as their genetic brand strategy, they create an emotion with their target audience by portraying a desirable lifestyle that consumers aspire to

achieve. This strategy often involves associating with a brand with a particular demographics, interest and activities with a special experience. Example Ibuprofen, advert for therapeutic relieve. In summary to this chapter, it is suggested that the genetic brand strategies and consumer satisfaction has a relationship to enhance the pharmaceutical industry in Rivers State. The brand heritage/tradition and personalization/customization will improve consumer satisfaction. The genetic brand strategies have positive effect to life style/aspiration. Personalization/customization are sometimes un predictable due to Brand Genetic influence. Genetic brand heritage /tradition perception trend can ripple the drips of a genetic strategies to brands personalization and customization and the life style aspiration for consumer satisfaction.

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

Empirical Review

2	iv. Rook (1985). shows the brands qualities	Kotler and Keller (2013)	The influence of Heritage/tradition with brand on customer satisfaction at Green pharmaceutical therapeutic industry.	The findings revealed that genetic brand strategies are significant to enhance customer satisfaction in pharmaceutical companies The study also reported that the genetic brand strategies dimensions that enhance customer satisfaction includes personalization/ customization lifestyle/aspiration and brand heritage/tradition
3		Kālu and Igwe 2008 (2017)	Heritage/tradition Brand proactive approach marketing practices, competitive environment and performance of moral responsibility to companies brand.	The findings revealed that genetic brand strategies has a significant relationship with personalization and customization the on heritage /tradition study also reported that competitive environment significantly moderates the relationship between genetic bran strategies and consumer satisfaction
4	Whaley	et al (2010)	The effect of brand heritage/tradition on life style /aspiration	The study reported that all the dimensions of brand heritage/tradition and life style/ aspiration to brand (providing relevant content, updating content, providing popular content on brand history

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the correlation survey research design. The target population of this study comprised of (21) registered pharmaceutical companies in Port Harcourt. Given a population of (21) pharmaceutical companies. The study adopted a census approach and undertook a study of the entire (21) therapeutic companies with a focus on the staff (brand medicine sales dispenser Managers). To generate data for the study, sixty-three (63) copies of questionnaire were given to the twenty-one registered pharmaceutical companies in the frame of three (3) copies per pharmaceutical company. The questionnaire was structured in a four (4) point Likert scale. The data collected through the questionnaire were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation through the aid of SPSS, version 21.0.

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

Questionnaire Distribution

Issued	63
Retrieved	54
Useful	50

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

From the table, the researcher issued 63 copies of the questionnaire, 54 copies were retrieved, and 50 copies were useful for the study.

Hypothesis 1

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between genetic branding strategies and customer satisfaction of pharmaceutical companies.

		Genetic brand strategies		customer satisfaction
Pearson (r)	Genetic brand strategies	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.752**
		Sig. (2 tailed)	.	.001
		N	50	50
	customer satisfaction	Correlation Coefficient	.752**	1.000
		Sig. (2 tailed)	.001	.
		N	50	50

**Correlation is significant at 0.01 levels (2 tailed); *Correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2 tailed)

Source: SPSS-Generated Output

The table above presents the result of bivariate analysis carried out between genetic brand strategies heritage/tradition of pharmaceutical industry in Port Harcourt. The result shows that heritage/tradition has a strong positive correlation with customer satisfaction of pharmaceutical industry. ($r = .752^{**}$) and this correlation is significant at 0.01 level as indicated by the symbol **. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This means that we then accept that there is a strong positive and significant relationship in brand heritage/tradition and customer satisfaction of pharmaceutical company.

Hypothesis 2

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between genetic brand strategies and customer satisfaction of pharmaceutical industry in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

		Genetic brand strategies		customer satisfaction
Pearson (r)	Genetic brand strategies	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.564**
		Sig. (2 tailed)	.	.001
		N	50	50
	customer satisfaction	Correlation Coefficient	.564**	1.000
		Sig. (2 tailed)	.001	.
		N	50	50

**Correlation is significant at 0.01 levels (2 tailed); *Correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2 tailed)

Source: SPSS-Generated Output

The table above presents the result of the bivariate analysis carried out Between Genetic Brand Strategies of Pharmaceutical Industry in Rivers State, from the table issued 63 copies of the questionnaire, 54 copies were retrieved and 50 copies were useful for the study.

The table presented above presents the result of the variate analysis carried out between Genetic Brand Strategy and Customer Satisfaction of pharmaceutical industry in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. ($r = .564^{**}$) and the symbol ** indicates that this correlation is significant at 0.01 level. Based on this, the result shows that Genetic Brand Strategy has a moderate positive correlation result, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

This means that, we then accept that there is a moderate positive significant relationship between Genetic Brand Strategy and customer satisfaction of the pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

- 1) There is a strong significant relationship between Genetic Brand Strategy and Customer Satisfaction of Pharmaceutical Port Harcourt.
- 2) There is a moderate and significant relationship between Genetic Brand Strategy and Customer Satisfaction of Pharmaceutical Industry.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the bivariate analysis carried, it was discovered that Genetic Brand Strategies showed a significant relationship with customer satisfaction of pharmaceutical therapeutic industry in Port Harcourt. It was viewed that genetic brand strategies showed a very strong and significant relationship with Customer Satisfaction of Pharmaceutical Therapeutic Industry in Rivers State. Building relationship is normally between the customer and the brand rather than the customer and the brand owner or a company. Brands are only identified and attract royalty mainly by consumers of the brand itself, which shows that not the owner or company or the industry that are attracted to brand but solely to the brand users seeking satisfaction.

These findings are supported by Andrew, Chinwe and Walters (2020) on genetic brand cross functional strategic brand theory, which states that Brand authenticity, innovation, customization, life style aspiration, and heritage are significant to customer satisfaction. Andrew (2020) Brand spans two levels, life style/aspiration and personalization/customization in the total product models. As brand is a part of heritage/tradition as it involves in customization. Keller (2014) asserts that to strategically managed brand with the four major managerial processes are involved in the analysis as Identified by CVSHealth care (2019), such as planning strategy/implementation, control/measurement.

Igwe (2016), human being are created unique and as such desire special and unique product to meet and compliment their peculiar needs and provide an opportunity for varieties of wants and choice. Comment to Igwe on brand (choice) is (known as genetic brand variation) In context of, heritage/tradition based on life style and aspiration to personality and customization as brand heritage for customer satisfaction if adopted. Chinwe and Walters (2020) agreed that genetic brand strategies are the bases of any brand can use as one of strategy for customer satisfaction, based on brand heritage and tradition chains of dimensions.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that genetic brand strategies are significant predictor, key drivers and influencer to customer satisfaction of pharmaceutical therapeutic industry. Based on these findings it is suggested that there will be a tremendous success if they adopt the tools and implement the genetic brand strategies with focus on heritage /tradition, life style/ aspiration and personalization /customization it will aid to profitable customer satisfaction in the pharmaceutical industry.

RECOMMENDATION

The study recommends that

- 1) Pharmaceutical therapeutic industry should ploy with the genetic brand strategies to determine the brand heritage /tradition to increase their demographical (all genders and ages) potential customer satisfaction based on the life style aspiration.
- 2) They should also adopt customization and personalisation. To reach out to right audience, to engage the value customers where satisfaction can be obtainable. The genetic brand strategies are easy and achievable to engage with, to aid the desired customer satisfaction.

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